

Co-Creating Circular
Resource Flows in Cities

constRuctive mEtabolic processes For materiaL fLOWs in
urban and peri-urban environments across Europe

Deliverable 6.2

COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

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Keywords	Capacity building, community of practice, stakeholders, best practice, knowledge sharing

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Abbreviations

BM	Business Model
CE	Circular Economy
COP	Community of Practice
WP	Work Package

Glossary

Capacity Building	The process by which individuals and organizations obtain, improve, and retain the skills, knowledge, tools, equipment and other resources needed to do their jobs competently or to a greater capacity
Centralised CoP	Centrally created and maintained by the Reflow project.
Circular Economy	A circular economy is an alternative to a traditional linear economy (make, use, dispose) in which we keep resources in use for as long as possible, extracting the maximum value from them whilst in use, then recovering and reusing products and materials. The circular economy concept proposes a regenerative system in which resource input and waste, emission and energy leakage are minimised by material loops. Within REFLOW, the focus of the circular economy gradually extends beyond issues related to material management and covers other aspects, such as social impact, technological aspects and the evolution of urban governance structures
Community of Practice	A group of people who share a set of problems, a joint concern or an interest in a topic. The community of practice comes together to fulfil both individual and group goals.
Community Stickiness	The gain to create are repeated interest by the community
De-centralised	Local community of practice by the six pilot cities.
Peri-urban	Areas located between rural to urban land
Regenerative City	A regenerative city moves beyond sustainability, and develops a restorative, mutually beneficial relationship with the natural and social systems that sustain it. In Reflow, the

	road to generative urban development will be achieved through the attention to the social, environmental, technological, and economic dimensions
Regenerative Economy	An approach in which products and services replenish their own sources of energy, water, and materials in a closed-loop system
Pilot	A small-scale test or experiment in the preparation for bigger activities at a later stage
Pilot City	The six pilot cities of the Reflow project: Amsterdam, Vejle, Berlin, Paris and Milan
Stakeholder	A group, organization, member, individual or system that affects or can be affected by an organization's actions

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15	MCS DATALABS	MCS	Germany
16	COMUNE DI MILANO	MILAN	Italy
17	WEMAKE S.R.L.	WMK	Italy
18	OPENDOT SRL	OD	Italy

19	FAB CITY GRAND PARIS	FCGP	France
20	COMMUNE DE PARIS	PARIS	France
21	ARS LONGA	ARSL	France
22	VOLUMES	VOL	France
23	VEJLE KOMMUNE	VEJLE	Denmark
24	DANSK DESIGN CENTER APS	DDC	Denmark
25	MUNICIPUL CLUJ-NAPOCA	CLUJ	Romania
26	FILIALA TRANSILVANIA A ASOCIATIEI ROMANE PENTRU INDUSTRIA ELECTRONICA SI DE SOFTWARE	ARIES	Romania
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1 Introduction

1.1 About Reflow

Reflow is an EU Horizon 2020 research project running from 2019-2022, which aims to enable the transition of European cities towards circular and regenerative practices. More specifically, Reflow uses Fab Labs and makerspaces as catalysers of a systemic change in urban and peri-urban environments, which enable, visualize, and regulate “four freedoms”: free movement of materials, people, (technological) knowledge and commons, to reduce materials consumption, maximize multifunctional use of (public) spaces and envisage regenerative practices. The project provides best practices aligning market and government needs to create favourable conditions for the public and private sector to adopt circular economy (CE) practices. Reflow is creating new CE business models within six pilot cities: Amsterdam, Berlin, Cluj-Napoca, Milan, Paris and Vejle and assess their social, environmental, and economic impact, by enabling active citizen involvement and systemic change to re-think the current approach to material flows in cities.

1.2 Reflow Vision

A circular and regenerative city in Reflow represents an urban system with social and business practices which place equal attention to **social, environmental, and economic impact**; where **technology** is open and represents a central enabler of positive social and environmental change; where the urban system ensures and support resilience of social and ecological systems; where **governance** is collaborative and inclusive; where **knowledge** is shared, and **stakeholders** are active and involved.

1.3 About the deliverable

This deliverable reports on how communities of practice have been created and maintained during Reflow. The communities served a two-fold purpose: 1) To gather feedback on their needs and ideas for capacity building resources and guidance materials created in other tasks of WP6, and 2) In general create a community related to circular and regenerative economy at urban and peri-urban level, for the benefit of the members.

Context and background

The Reflow project mission is to support the development of cities that are regenerative and adopt circular economy practices, through the re-localisation of production and the reconfiguration of material flows. Reflow’s approach to circular economy is distinctive for two main specific reasons. On the one hand, it has a broader approach to circular economy that does not limit itself to an environmental analysis but also includes the social side of sustainability by providing a set of measures on the social impact of Circular innovation. Moreover, Reflow focuses on the evolution of governance structures within cities, as well as on the technological innovation that allows the transition to circular economy to take place.

Reflow explores circular innovation using a digital and physical network of public institutions, scientific institutions, makerspaces, and other grass-root organisations in six pilot cities: Amsterdam, Berlin, Cluj-Napoca, Milan, Paris, and Vejle. These pilots work closely with scientific and technical organisations in Europe to provide

guidance for public and private sector organisations on how to create favourable conditions for the adoption of circular and regenerative practices.

Achieving circular and regenerative cities is not only about developing new and innovative solutions, but importantly also about ensuring that the relevant stakeholders necessary to realise the transition understand and have the necessary competencies to execute on the solutions. An important part of the Reflow Project therefore also revolves around capacity building both internally in the consortium, and more importantly, in connection with the local communities and on a European level. To achieve this, the Reflow project has worked on developing, sustaining, and supporting a range of *Communities of Practices*, with the aim to strengthen the general practice of circular economy as well as ensuring the adoption of solutions developed in Reflow. These communities have been **both centrally and de-centrally** (or locally) managed, being both **digital** and **physical**. By creating community of practices, Reflow aimed to activate these individuals in sharing knowledge and inspiring practices to build a common understanding of the transition pathways that support the development of circular cities, both during and expectantly after the end of the project.

The below figure illustrates the relation between the centralised CoP and the Decentralised CoP, and how the Reflow partners have cross-pollinated amongst themselves and other communities.

Figure 1. Overview of Reflow's CoP. Source: Ecovala

1.4 Connection to the Reflow Framework and other deliverables

The Reflow Framework lays out a way to work towards circular and regenerative cities, through several levels of focused action: Material Innovation, Product and Tech Innovation, Circular Business Model Innovation, Socio-Technical Innovation, and lastly Validation and Performance Management. The Reflow Framework is further

explained in D1.3 – The Reflow Framework. For the relevant stakeholders to be able to work both within and across these levels, Capacity Building plays a pivotal role and consequently Communities of Practice, where the members can be inspired on what a successful transition can look like, be informed and build awareness on the approaches that can be undertaken to successfully transition, to connect with other circular stakeholders within cities and beyond, and last but not least, to be equipped with the rights tools, methods, processes to transform. This way, Community of Practice does not belong to any specific part of the Framework but acts as an enabler across and between.

Figure 2. The Reflow Framework. Source: CBS

Looking at the connection with other deliverables, D6.2 is highly interconnected with WP6 and WP7. Being within the same overall focus, this is particularly for the other deliverables in WP6; Capacity Building and Knowledge Transfer. Most importantly, the first communities created by Reflow had the aim to provide input on the content of the Capacity building toolkit, which is described in D6.1 Capacity Building Framework. The Multi-Platform digital resources developed and reported in D6.4 constitute relevant content and resources used by the different communities of practice, and so does the developed open-source collaborative learning case studies reported in D6.5 – Collaborative Case Studies for Higher Education, and lastly D6.3 – Capacity Building Toolkit, which reports on the various digital resources developed in the framework of the Reflow project aims at supporting individuals and organisations acquire the skills, knowledge and tools support the transition of cities towards circularity.

The deliverable is also connected to work package 7; WP7; Dissemination, Exploitation, and Sustainability, and of these, particularly dissemination. A community of practice is about sharing knowledge and connecting and collaborating with other actors in the field. In D7.3, such activities are reported in a quantitative way, proving the analysis of consortium wide activities and events and the involved external actors. Comparably, D6.2 provides a

more qualitative record of how Reflow has engaged in communities. Such interactions and their contribution are also reported on in D7.4; Collaboration with covenant of Mayors and External Communities. This deliverable is however more goal oriented and focused on how such external interaction has contributed to providing relevant feedback of the work of Reflow and given validation to the solutions developed. Comparably, D6.2 is less focused on the concrete and measurable results of community activities and is based on a more open and fluid understanding of how Reflow has taken part in and contributed to the global and local communities of practice. Lastly, the expectation is that the communities of practice developed during Reflow continue to enable the discussion and knowledge sharing around circularity in cities, and thereby take part in the ongoing exploitation of Reflow, reported on in D7.5 – Sustainability and Business Plans.

1.5 Structure of the report

The report is divided into three main chapters: 1) Introducing the concept of Communities of Practice, 2) Describing the centralised Communities of Practice, and 3) Describing the De-centralised Communities of Practice.

The first chapter presents the concept of Communities of Practice and how the term has been understood and used in the context of Reflow. The second chapter describes the Centralised CoP, referring to the Forum and LinkedIn Group created and administrated by Reflow. The chapter is further broken down into sub-sections, presenting how the centralised CoP's where created, maintained, iterated half-way through the project, and the final evaluation and reflections. The second chapter outline the de-centralised CoP's, and how these have been created by the individual pilot cities as well as across pilots, before rounding up with reflections.

2 Community of Practice – what are we talking about?

2.1 The theoretical understanding of Community of Practice

A community of practice can be defined as "a group of professionals informally bound to one another through exposure to a common class of problems, common pursuit of solutions, and thereby themselves embodying a store of knowledge"¹.

A community of practice consists of members who interact with each other for their pursuit of a common practice. It is therefore this collective social practice that links individuals together across official organisational boundaries and makes up the community. Communities of practice often focus on sharing best practices and creating new knowledge to advance a domain of professional practice. Interaction on an ongoing basis is an important part of this. Communities of practice may rely on face-to-face meetings as well as web-based collaborative environments to communicate, connect and conduct community activities. However, the interaction does not have to be in-between all members of the community and can be infrequent. And although

¹ Botha A, Kourie D, & Snyman R, (2008), Coping with Continuous Change in the Business Environment, Knowledge Management and Knowledge Management Technology, Chandice Publishing Ltd

communities of practice are focused on learning from each other and together, the definition does not require that learning is always intentional. It can also be an incidental outcome of member's interactions².

Today, communities of practices are increasingly being used to improve knowledge management and connect people within business, government, education, and other organisations. Communities of practice are increasingly seen as relevant as they connect people who might not otherwise interact, either as frequently or at all. They provide a shared context for people to communicate and share information, stories and personal experiences in a way that builds understanding and insight. They enable dialogue between people who come together to explore new possibilities, solve challenging problems, and create new, mutually beneficial opportunities. They stimulate learning by serving as a vehicle for authentic communication, mentoring, coaching, and self-reflection. Communities of practice are formed by people who engage in a process of collective learning in a shared domain of human endeavour: a tribe learning to survive, a band of artists seeking new forms of expression, a group of engineers working on similar problems, a clique of pupils defining their identity in the school, a network of surgeons exploring novel techniques, a gathering of first-time managers helping each other cope.

To be defined as a community of practice, three interconnected dimensions need to be revealed: the domain, the community, and the practice:

The domain: A community of practice is not merely a club of individuals or a network of connections between people. It has an identity defined by a shared domain of interest. Being part of the community therefore implies a commitment to the domain, and therefore a shared competence that distinguishes members from other people.

The community: In pursuing their interest in their domain, members engage in joint activities and discussions, help each other, and share information. They build relationships that enable them to learn from each other. A website in itself is not a community of practice. Having the same job or the same title does not make for a community of practice unless members interact and learn together. Members of a community of practice do not necessarily work together daily, but the regular interactions are essential to making them a community of practice.

The practice: A community of practice is not merely a community of interest. Members of a community of practice are practitioners. They develop a shared repertoire of resources: experiences, stories, tools, ways of addressing recurring problems—in short, a shared practice. The development of a shared practice may be more or less self-conscious. By actively engaging with one another, members of the community can develop a set of shared stories and cases that have become a shared repertoire for their practice.

The design of the community will look different depending on the purpose and needs of the participants. Four types of communities can be designed: **Helping Communities** which provide a forum for community members to help each other with everyday work needs. **Best Practice Communities** which develop and disseminate best practices, guidelines, and strategies for their members' use. **Knowledge Stewarding Communities** which

² Wenger, Etienne and Beverly Wenger-Trayner (2015). Introduction to communities of practice A brief overview of the concept and its uses. <https://wenger-trayner.com/introduction-to-communities-of-practice/>

organize, manage, and steward a body of knowledge from which community members can draw. **Innovation Communities**, which create breakthrough ideas, new knowledge, and new practices³. The lines between these types are blurred and overlapping, particularly the three first one which all enable the sharing of existing knowledge although with a varying degree of facilitation, whereas the latter focuses more on the creation of new knowledge. Further, the rather organic nature of CoPs might result in the type changing over time based on the needs and behaviours of the members.

Together, the different CoPs support a set of key objectives:

- Capture and share existing knowledge to help people improve their practice by providing a collaborative space to identify solutions to common challenges and a process to collect and evaluate best practices.
- Introduce collaborative processes to groups and organizations to encourage the free flow of ideas and exchange of information.
- Help people organize around purposeful actions that develop tangible results.
- Generate new knowledge to help people transform their practice to accommodate changes in needs and technologies.

2.2 Reflow's approach to Community of Practice

As described in the introduction, the aim of creating CoPs in Reflow was 1) To gather input to the capacity building resources as described in other deliverables of WP6, and 2) To facilitate the capacity building between stakeholders interested and active in the transition to circular and regenerative societies. The capacity building was seen as both spreading knowledge and best practices about circularity in cities, equip those interested with the tools and methods, create spaces for innovation and new ideas, and overarchingly enable a sense of collectiveness.

As described in the theoretical section, a CoP can be both face-to-face meetings as well as web-based collaborative environments to communicate, connect and conduct community activities, as long as there is a minimum of interaction (it can be in-frequent and does not have to be in-between all members). As Reflow operates both at local level with pilot cities interventions, and at European level with a set of supporting actors delivering specific methodologies and transition instruments, it was relevant to design the operationalization of the community as an hybrid approach at both levels: **1) An online collaborative space** in which all actors are invited to share their knowledge and learn from each other, and **2) A collection of local hubs**, in which local stakeholders are able to meet physically to tackle challenges and co-design new knowledge and solutions. Reflow Project therefore deployed two strategies for the creation of CoPs: **a centralised and controlled web-based CoP**, and several **de-centralised and local CoPs**, originating from the six pilot cities, which developed in an organic, self-guided and uncontrolled manner.

The overarching domain of the two has been the same: *the transformation to regenerative and circular cities*, appealing to those who have a shared interest in the topic, and thus distinguishing themselves from other people. However, the type of community has been differentiated, meaning the way the members have engaged, and

³ Wenger, Etienne and Beverly Wenger-Trayner (2015). Introduction to communities of practice A brief overview of the concept and its uses. <https://wenger-trayner.com/introduction-to-communities-of-practice/>

different CoPs have appealed to different specialisations within the topic. This hybrid approach was created both to reach wider and deeper in terms of members, as more specialised CoPs reach other types of people than those with a more general topic, and as a response to the distributed nature of the Reflow Project and its consortium. Consisting of partners across 28 European countries and the goal to engage with relevant stakeholders across Europe, called for an online community that allowed for easy and frequent interaction despite being at different locations. The six pilot cities and their respective material focus however, called for more local and face-to-face communities. Lastly, the two different approaches were also affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. One year after the initiation of the project, face-to-face meeting and events were no longer possible, and the communities were forced to move online both centrally and de-centrally. With the (to some extent) opening of society following the increased control with the pandemic, the pilot cities were again able to engage face-to-face with their CoPs again at the end of the Reflow Project.

Overarchingly, the Reflow identifies multiple stakeholders who have a potential interest in the project knowledge development, and which were then the overall target groups of both centralised and de-centralised CoPs. These target groups which are summarized below.

Target group	Description	Interest in sharing practices
A – Industry Stakeholders	Urban manufacturers and their associations as well as technology providers, in particular those operating in the domains directly related with Reflow.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of project’s learnings in everyday operations - Training on project’ outcomes - Inspiration for new business models and application
B – Fab Labs and makerspaces	Grassroots organisations, open to the public that offer tools and services for digital manufacturing, thus promoting social and economic innovation.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of project’s learnings in everyday operations - Training on project’ outcomes - Inspiration for new ideas and application
C – Public administrations	Other EU municipalities which could be interested in adopting CE practices and tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of project’s learnings in everyday operations - Training on project’ outcomes - Inspiration for new policies and application
D – EU Associations and Clusters	European initiatives and clusters, e.g., Covenant of Mayors, C40, Fab City Global Initiative.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dissemination of project's knowledge to their members

E – Circular Economy Stakeholders	Participants, external partners and other relevant stakeholders active in EU projects and other initiatives.	- Identification of common topics
F – Research & Academia	Individuals engaged in research initiatives and/or working in research/academic institutes conducting research on Circular Economy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - knowledge acquisition - use of knowledge in teaching - Inspiration for future research initiatives based on the project’s concept and results
G – Policy Makers	Policy makers at local, regional and national level, such as public authorities, regulatory agencies and ministries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of project’s learnings in everyday operations - Training on project’ outcomes - Inspiration for new policies and application
H – General Public	End users who benefit from the project outcomes, civil society.	- Knowledge acquisition

Table 1: Overview of Reflow target groups

3 Centralised Circular Community of Practice

3.1 Introduction

The Reflow Project sought to ensure capacity building both internally in the consortium, and more importantly, on a European level for all target audiences defined by the project. The aim was to both share general knowledge and tools necessary to facilitate circular city transitions, communicate the new knowledge and tools developed within the Reflow project, and activate the audiences in sharing knowledge and inspiring practices to build a common

understanding of the transition pathways, making it a combination of a *Best Practice* and *Knowledge Stewarding Community*.

To achieve this, the CoP was set-up as web-based collaborative environments to communicate, connect and conduct community activities, allowing the information to be spread widely, and enable connection between people who do not normally connect, both across boards and fields. Concretely, the centralised CoP consisted of an online *Forum* and a *LinkedIn group*. The Forum has been part of a dedicated 24/7 online space for collaboration, discussion, archiving meetings and webinars, and sharing resources has been designed as part of the Reflow website, called "Community", which integrated all knowledge sharing resources developed throughout the project duration: the Reflow Best Practice Database, Reflow Academy, and the Knowledge Hub.

All these online capacity building resources can be argued to have contributed to the centralised CoP, as they have all taken part in disseminate best practices, guidelines, and strategies for those interesting in the work of Reflow and circular cities specifically. However, the forum and the LinkedIn Group are the only one of these that allows for interaction between the users, and required an active choice to be a member, respectively to sign up and / or request membership. this deliverable focusses only on this aspect,

This way, the Forum and LinkedIn group differed from the other knowledge sharing efforts in the "Community", and where there was no possibility for dialogue with and between the visitors, and thereby do not classify as CoPs. That said, the curated information given through the Reflow Website, the newsletter, and the LinkedIn Page, in some way also represent Best Practice CoPs, as the visitors of these online spaces can be believed to have a sense of passive connection with each other through being interested in the same field. The reach and audience of these resources can be found in in *D6.3 - Capacity Building Toolkit*, and *D7.3 - Communication and Dissemination Activities Report*.

The following chapter goes through 1) How the first communities contributed to the capacity building materials of Reflow, and 2) the work with the Forum as the main CoP, and how the LinkedIn Group complemented the effort. The chapter starts out with a description of the Forum, including how it was developed and what it contained, before presenting the evaluation done in M29 and the subsequent interventions, which included a re-formulation of the LinkedIn Group. The chapter concludes with the final evaluation and reflections on the success and impact of the centralised CoP.

3.2 Input to the Capacity Building Materials

To tailor the training resources to the needs of active stakeholders at city level, it was necessary to first identify and assess the skills and competences needed for each stakeholder and second, prioritize the skills that should be developed further based on existing levels of competence, and finally to grasp how individuals generally want to learn. After the first six months of the Reflow project, an online questionnaire was therefore developed and distributed to the members of the consortium representing pilot cities, the associated partners providing supporting roles at EU level, and external stakeholders. Their input gave an important contribution which helped define the direction and content of the capacity building resources and guidance material, and thus represented the first communities of practice developed by Reflow.

The full report, including methodology and results can be found in Appendix 1.

3.3 The Forum: The Reflow Circular Cities Community

Figure 3: Screenshot of the frontpage of the Forum

3.3.1 The development of the Forum

The processes of designing and creating the forum started at the very beginning of the Reflow Project, leading up to launch the 1st of September 2019.

Figure 4 provides an overview of the development of the forum, starting out with the creation, which included the framing of the *domain*, defining how to make a *community*, how to create a community which develop *shared practices*, and how to *recruit* to the forum. In month 29 of the Project, the forum was subject to a mid-term evaluation and a subsequent intervention aimed at correcting any unintended aspects and improving it. Lastly, the forum was evaluated according to how it performed according to the aim.

Figure 4: The forums development process

3.3.1.1 Framing of the domain

The community of practice was framed around the domain of circular cities. A circular city is about a great deal more than creating a circular economy and circular business models within the urban context. It is about the regeneration and renewal of complex urban ecosystems⁴. Circular cities

⁴Williams, J. (2019). SAGE journals. Circular cities. Retrieved from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/0042098018806133>

can be characterised by a set of guiding principles, framed into a specific scope, and supported by a set of complementary actions.

Below is an overview of the anticipated domain of interest characterizing the forum:

1. Circular city principles

- Regeneration of the urban system: the ecosystem supporting the city functions is constantly regenerated, ecosystem services are preserved, and natural capital is protected.
- Reduction of resource consumption: Resources used to sustain city functions are reduced on one hand and reused (looped) in the system on other hand.
- Negative externalities at social environmental and economic levels are designed out.

2. Circular city scope

- Circular cities are bounded in the urban ecosystem
- Resources addressed are materials, energy, water, land, and infrastructure
- Scale: combination of macro (city level) and meso (city districts) and micro levels (inhabitants)
- Focus: lifestyle, social practices, systems of provision.
- Activities: production and consumption patterns related to housing, mobility, food, leisure, education, through cross sector interactions.

3. Circular city actions

- Closing resource loops (through recycling, recovery, reuse of resources)
- Plan and adapt cities to be adaptable, resilient, and regenerative.
- Focus on re-localisation of production to develop local symbiotic activities
- Substitution of non-renewables with renewables in the value chain, substitution of resource-based activities with service-based activities, substitution of physical artefacts with dematerialized artefacts.
- Optimization of resource usage through sharing practices and the use of enabling technologies.

In addition, an online survey was sent to members of the community, both inside and outside of the project consortium, to understand more about how they saw the forum, why/why not they would be active in the forum, which CE topics they found interesting, and which features they wanted from the forum.

From this it came out that:

- The majority saw a benefit from joining an online community, if it provided knowledge, inspiration and opportunities, but that a reason not to join would be if it becomes overloaded and unstructured.
- The majority found the topics of citizen practice, circular business models and circular policies the most interesting.
- Regarding features of the forum, the most important were 1) The possibility to upload/share knowledge, 2) Great user experience, 3) A critical mass of active members, 4) That it integrates with other platforms, such as LinkedIn, and 5) That it provides a good overview of knowledge and is up to date.
- The main aspects that would limit participation was lack of time.

The report of the survey can be found in Appendix 2.

3.3.1.2 Characterising the community

In the context of Reflow, the community was comprised of several layers:

- *Practitioners* specialised in circular and regenerative cities (city servants, consultants, and other intermediaries). These practitioners are initially part of the project consortium (involved stakeholders of the pilot cities, supporting actors at European level), but the aim is to extend the core group to other stakeholders active in other European cities.
- Beyond practitioners, the community of practice aims to include additional *policy research institutes, think-tanks and policy advisors* who support practitioners in their day-to-day management.
- Finally, *educationalists*, who translate the insights of practitioners and researchers, allow through their work to disseminate knowledge to new stakeholders (students, aspiring professionals, etc...).

3.3.1.3 Framing of the practice

Practices around circular economy acceleration at city scale are diverse. Below are examples of practices that were expected to be shared between practitioners through the forum:

- Co-design of shared narratives and visions
- Development of urban metabolism diagnosis
- Establishment of roadmaps and actions plans
- Systematization of regulation policies towards circular economy
- Organize incentives and fundings
- Setting space for pilots and experimentations
- Business model innovation
- Developing impact frameworks
- Engagement practices with diverse stakeholders
- Capacity building, education towards circular economy.

3.3.1.4 Recruitment strategy

Once the domain, actors' typologies and practices were clearly defined, the next phase was to identify the practitioners and supporting actors who are currently working around the domain and invite them to participate in the community of practice.

The recruitment happened in two phases:

- 1 **Internal population:** Invitation sent to the first core of the community: the consortium members of the Reflow project constituted the first stakeholders invited to join the community and actively participated in the activities set by the community.
- 2 **Invitation to externals:** Invitation to specific and identifiable individuals recognised in the domain/field. See Table 2. Table 2: Invitation to potential Forum members
- 3 **Snowball strategy.** In turn, each core member was encouraged to invite actors from their ecosystem who may see interest in participating

Who are We?

We are a community of individuals, active around the regeneration of cities: Researchers, activists, consultants, policy makers, driven by the need to accelerate the transition of cities towards more circular and regenerative practices.

What is our Vision?

Reflow community of practice is an online platform for cities, businesses, and citizens to explore, share and implement circular practices and strategies to tackle urban challenges.

By encouraging knowledge exchange and co-creation, we aim to break down information silos and fuel multi-stakeholder collaboration and innovation.

We aim to create online and offline conversations that support each member of the community on their daily activities towards circular cities transition.

What do we want to share?

We want to share innovative activities, business models, reports and policies that support regenerative and circular cities.

Table 2: Invitation to potential Forum members

In addition to the recruitment, a CoP is dependent on continues interaction and engagement, and for this is it crucial to ensure potential participants have an incentive to participate; community members need to feel that the time and effort they will put into the experience will give them something back.

The following aspects were therefore identified as strategic ways to ensure participation by securing value for time, and served as a guide for the Reflow administrators when monitoring the forum:

- Choosing issues that are timely for all participants and based on their daily work
- Describing how their input will make a difference
- Offering resources (access to direct knowledge, tools, and successful case studies)
- Generating excitement about collaborating to find new solutions.

When issuing the invitation, we need to describe the structure of the community of practice and the work of this community sufficiently so that potential participants will understand what they will be committing to.

3.3.1.5 Anticipated interventions and evaluation

Different interventions (activities) were foreseen to activate the community.

- **Creating a who's who of the community.** The forum should allow community members to create a profile page detailing their expertise, involvement on circular city practices. This function will allow other members to discover other members of the community.

- **Mapping knowledge resources:** members of the community are invited to share existing knowledge on publications, reports, tools, practical initiatives (e.g.: providing information on a circular city initiative).
- **Request for information** (e.g.: *Are you aware of specific tools to perform an activity?*)
- **Seeking experience in relation to problem solving** (e.g.: *How have you solved issue of citizen engagement?*)
- **Build synergies** (e.g.: *We are looking at developing a new EU project, we are looking for experts in material flow analysis*)
- **Provide feedback on tools/methodologies developed within Reflow.**

From the beginning, evaluations in M29 and M36 were foreseen. As an online forum, the participation and impact could be rather easily evaluated through quantitative approaches. Potential qualitative impact was considered too intangible to assess. The evaluation was designed as a **Participation data evaluation**, asking questions such as: How active is the community? e.g., How many people are participating? How often? What kind of activities do they engage in?

These questions were measured according to the following metrics:

- 1 Registered members
- 2 New sign ups
- 3 New pageviews
- 4 Anonymous pageviews
- 5 Logged in pageviews
- 6 Community 'stickiness'
- 7 New topics
- 8 Created posts
- 9 Likes

The results of the evaluation will be presented in section 3.4.

3.3.2 Reflow forum overview

The Forum is hosted at the following address: <https://forum.reflowproject.eu>. It is built on the open-source DISCOURSE software, which served two purposes: 1) To reduce the resources needed to establish the forum by building on an established and tested template, and 2) To support the open-source vision of DISCOURSE.

Discourse

Discourse is an open-source Internet forum and mailing list management software application founded in 2013. From a usability perspective, Discourse breaks with existing forum software by including features recently popularized by large social networks, such as infinite scrolling, live updates, expanding links, and drag and drop attachments. However, the stated goals of the project are social rather than technical, to improve online discussion quality through improved forum software.

The source code is distributed under the GNU General Public License version 2. Therefore, Discourse can be self-hosted by anyone. Alternatively, hosting service can be bought from the company of the founders. As of July 2020, more than 1,500 businesses or instances have chosen this option.

Table 3: Discourse software

Figure 5: forum home page

When creating a user and entering the forum, the visitors could see both the most recent topics on the left side or browse different categories. The first post everyone would see, was one that welcomed them to the community, introducing the forum and giving a short explanation of Reflow, the vision, the aim of the forum, and how to get in touch with the administrators.

Categories of the forum:

The categories sought to break down the topic of circular and regenerative cities into more specific elements, to enable easier identification of relevant topics for the rather broad target audience, and in turn create more concrete discussions.

WHAT'S NEW

Read the latest news about circular economy initiatives

CIRCULAR PROJECTS

Involved in a Circular City initiative? Share your insights!

CIRCULAR RESEARCH

Discuss about research topics, academic collaborations, publications, dissertation, theses focusing on circular cities

CIRCULAR LEARNING RESOURCES

Aware of a new educational course or material, share it here!

CIRCULAR ECONOMY TOOLKITS

Introduce your tools and methodologies that support the transition to circular cities

CIRCULAR CHALLENGES

Have a burning issue you want to share to the community?

REFLOW OS

Discuss anything related to Tech solutions for city circularity

WHO'S WHO

Take 5 minutes to introduce yourself to the community

UNCATEGORIZED

Topics that don't need a category, or don't fit into any other existing category.

Table 4: Categories of the Forum

Users were also introduced to Rules of Engagement:

Rules of Engagement
<p>Who are We?</p> <p>We are a community of individuals, active around the regeneration of cities: Researchers, activists, consultants, policy makers, driven by the need to accelerate the transition of cities towards more circular and regenerative practices.</p>
<p>What is our Vision?</p> <p>Reflow Community of Practice is an online platform for cities, businesses, and citizens to explore, share and implement circular practices and strategies to tackle urban challenges.</p> <p>By encouraging knowledge exchange and co-creation, we aim to break down information silos and fuel multi-stakeholder collaboration and innovation.</p>
<p>What do we want to share?</p> <p>We want to share Innovative activities, business models, report, policies that support regenerative and circular cities.</p>
<p>A couple of rules</p> <p>Things we encourage:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Free sharing of knowledge, insights, opinions and disruptive ideas!• Respect fellow Reflowers as human beings, along with the diversity of our members' backgrounds, perspectives, education, and experiences.• Be supportive of each other.• Be polite and friendly.• Be tolerant and considerate.• Act professionally, ethically and with integrity. <p>Things we discourage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Do not behave in an abusive, demeaning, discriminatory, defamatory, or harassing manner.• Do not engage in personal attacks. <p>Unacceptable Content</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Spam.• Content copied and posted without the permission of the content owner (e.g., text, photos, videos).• Posts which are of duplicate content, whether from a single account or across multiple accounts from the same user, within the community. Please note that syndicated or cross-posted content is allowed if the source of content is stated. <p>Grounds for Rejections of Posts</p> <p>There are a few things you cannot do in the Reflow Community. These are actions that could lead to removal of your content.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1 Defaming another member: Posting content that discriminates against members based on any perceived differences, including but not limited to differences in culture, race, ethnicity, age, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity or expression, and physical ability.2 Copyright infringement: all content submitted to the Reflow Community be original content created by the author or reproduced with the permission of the copyright owner.

Table 5: Rules of Engagement

3.3.3 Evaluation

QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION OF THE FORUM M29

Approximately 1,5 years after the launch of the forum, the **Participation data evaluation** was undertaken. The forums data is derived from the website’s analytics dashboard. The data is presented quarterly, showing data from the launch of the forum in September 2019 until November 2021, when the evaluation was conducted.

Figure 6: Registered members, new sign-ups, new topics and likes (Sept. 2019 – Nov. 2021)

Figure 7: Page views (Sept. 2019 – Nov. 2021)

In November the forum had 84 registered members. After a slow start, the forum had a surge in new members between June and August 2020, correlating with new published topics and created posts. However, after August 2020, the inflow of new sign ups steadily decreased. Even though there was an increase in new published topics

and posts created between March and May 2021, it had little effect on gaining new members, and was mainly done by members from the Reflow Consortium.

Based on likes, Figure 6 shows that the engagement was low. At the forum’s “peak” between June and August 2020, likes amounted to a total of 24 in the duration of the three months period. This, despite increasing number of page views which is illustrated in Figure 7.

With the launch of the Reflow forum, coupled with its initial marketing efforts, the forum had an initial 8000 page views in its first quarter of its existence. However, page views started to drop, as there were not enough marketing and dissemination efforts and the few active members in this period (see Figure 6), did not incite new users to register and become active. A new push in March 2020 to establish activity in the forum was initiated, with creation of new topics and posts. The efforts gave a renewed boost to *new page visitors* as well as *new sign ups*. Successively, page views continued to increase throughout November 2021.

Figure 8: Community ‘stickiness’ (Sept. 2019 – Nov. 2021)

Community stickiness is a measure for user engagement and indicates how many times the same user returns to the website. It is calculated by number of members that logged in in the last day divided by the number of members that logged in in the last month. A percentage above 30 is good. Having users constantly coming back, shows that the content brings value to the visitor. Figure 8 illustrates that that the community stickiness for the Reflow forum has been overall decent. After a peak in March–May 2020, community stickiness stabilised on an average of 20%, which is satisfactory. From August and November 2021, the stickiness increased, indicating that members were pleased with the content on the website.

Overall, between September 2019 and November 2021, the website saw little success in terms of interaction - its initial purpose to act as a community of practice where members can “meet” and learn from each other and together. On the other hand, the forum had potential in terms of disseminating high quality information. Decent values on community stickiness showed that members visited the forum frequently for the information that was there.

During the evaluation in M29, the question of whether an online forum was indeed the best format for facilitating an active discussion between the target audience, was explored. To answer this question, a comparative analysis, one expert interview and desk research was conducted:

1. Comparative analysis

A comparison between different other options, judging each one’s ability to meet the following requirements, as defined by the ideal outcomes of an online CoP:

Figure 9: Platform analysis

	FORUM	LINKEDIN	SLACK	REDDIT
ACCESSIBLE	✗	✓	✗	✓
LIBRARY WITH FILTER	✓	✗	✗	✗
DIALOGUE	✓	✓	✓	✓
CONNECT	✓	✓	✓	✗
INFORMAL	✗	✗	✓	✓
FEED	✓	✓	✓	✓
PROFESSIONAL	✓	✓	✗	✗
SUM	5	5	4	4

Figure 10: Platform analysis

The conclusion was, unsurprisingly, that different format comes with pros and cons, but that for the needs of the Reflow Project, a forum in combination with a LinkedIn Group is indeed the platform that meets the most requirements.

2. Expert interview with Floris van der Marel

An interview was conducted with an experienced community manager, Floris van der Marel, Researcher and Facilitator of Participatory Design at Aalto University and Swinburne University of Technology: The interview explored questions such as the feasibility of creating active, online communities, and how it can potentially succeed. Three main learnings came out of the interview:

- a. Creating a purely online community is challenging, and time consuming. Often, an online community is kept alive through “energy injections” from physical events. And as each physical event can only contribute with a small and time limited injections, there is a need for many physical activities, often coming from many different projects. Consequently, it is likely only those organisations with many connected members and who are spread over many projects, which manage to generate enough energy into the online platform. This becomes even more difficult with a project that ends after a comparably short time, such as Reflow.
- b. There is seemingly a tendency of “online fatigue”, where many, including those dedicated to the topic, are overwhelmed by too many initiatives, websites, and places to check, and keep updated on. The platform should therefore rather be on an arena where the target audience is already at, to benefit from and build on the stickiness of other platforms.
- c. There isn’t a “one size fits all” – that can be both an archive, enable dialogue, and be updated and relevant on a day-to-day basis.

3. Desktop research on other circular economy organisations and their engagement with forums:

Several of the most known and similar organisations were investigated, including The Ellen MacArthur Foundation, Circle Economy, and The Nordic Circular Arena. Out of these three, only the latter has created a forum, which at the time of investigation was rather new, and had still not managed to create an active dialogue between users.

3.3.4 Corrective actions and intervention

Based on the above-described evaluation and research, it was decided that the forum served well as an archive for relevant information, and still had the potential to foster slower but deeper dialogues. However, it was acknowledged that the forum would not be able to cover the need for day-to-day communication and updates on events, as this information has a short expiration date and therefore should be located at a platform where the target audience already visits frequently and regularly. It was therefore decided to redefine the purpose of the Reflow LinkedIn group to encourage more sharing of smaller news and updates on this platform instead.

Forum intervention

To ease the navigation of the forum, and through this potentially increase user satisfaction and consequently visits and stickiness, the front page of the forum was changed. The changes were: 1) Pinning the three topics with the most interactions to the top of the page, 2) Moving away from a split front page between *categories* and *recent topics*, and rather let the user choose which one to display, and 3) A re-design of the category logos to make them better reflect the respective topic. Screenshots of the changes can be seen at the end of this sub-section.

LinkedIn Group intervention

To encourage a more active use of the Reflow LinkedIn Group, three interventions were done:

1. **New name and purpose:** To better differentiate the LinkedIn group from the LinkedIn Page, the group changed name from *Reflow Project* to *Reflow Circular Cities Community*, and presented its new purpose, see **Error! Reference source not found..** With this, the group was made more open to anyone interested in the topic, and not just those interested or connected to the Reflow project. Simultaneously, the existing members were also encouraged to invite their connections and share their own news, thoughts, topics and resources.
2. **Presentation of members:** To make the group more personal and human, a weekly introduction of a member was initiated, including a picture, a description of the members connection to the topic, and a personal funfact.
3. **Reflow Digest:** The group admins started a weekly tradition of posting a “Reflow Digest” every Friday. The post summarised different aspects relevant to circularity in cities, such as the weeks news, upcoming events, interesting learning resources, literature, inspiring cases of circular businesses, and a link to the forum to continue the conversation.

Figure 11: New purpose of LinkedIn Group

Betsy Akins (she/her) • 1st
Service designer finding beauty in unexpected places
8mo

We're excited to share our first **#REFLOWDigest** with you! Every Friday we will share a list of upcoming events, recent articles, and exciting innovations that we think might interest our community.

If you have something you want to share with the community, send us a message before Thursday. Also, feel free to add additional links in the comments section. Happy Friday!

📰 IN THE NEWS:

- The EU is giving citizens the "right to repair" electronics — here's what that could mean for the world bit.ly/3yUDrBr

📅 WHERE TO MINGLE:

- 13-15/09/21: World Circular Economy Forum 2021 www.wcef2021.com
- 14/09/2021: **#EUCircularTalks**: Green digital passport: Product traceability to create circular material loops <https://lnkd.in/gCFwbkyF>
- 29-30/09/21: makingitcircular.com/ the European circular challenge for makers
- 4-8/10/21: The Daring Cities 2021 global virtual forum daringcities.org

🏠 LEARNING CORNER:

- Join the cities future academy www.cityfutures.se

📖 WHAT WE'RE READING:

- Transformative Pathways to Sustainability bit.ly/3nitA5A
- Cities, Nature and Innovation: New Directions bit.ly/3tsFU4W
- Read the "Circular is..." catalogue bit.ly/3E4KlaZ

🏆 CIRCULAR BUSINESS OF THE WEEK:

- Krill Design makes a 3D-printed lamp using orange peel. <https://lnkd.in/ge4wqJDT>

🗣️ CONTINUE THE CONVERSATION:

- Learn and exchange about circular cities in the Reflow community orum.reflowproject.eu/

[#sustainability](#) [#environment](#) [#circulareconomy](#) [#reflowproject](#)

Figure 12: Example of one Reflow Digest

Figure 13: Screenshot of new front page

Figure 14: Screenshot of new logos for categories

3.3.4.1 Quantitative evaluation M36

After the first evaluation in M29, a new evaluation was made in May 2022, to check the status of the forum. The data is presented quarterly, starting from the launch of the forum in September 2019 and until May 5th, 2022.

Figure 15: Registered members, new sign-ups, new topics and likes (September 2019 – May 2022)

Figure 16: Page views (September 2019 – May 2022)

After the evaluation in M29 it was decided that the forum served well as an archive for relevant information, which could foster slower but deeper dialogs. The more interactive part was hence “moved” to the Reflow LinkedIn page, where its purpose was redefined. On this page, a more targeted effort to encourage more sharing of smaller news and updates where initiated,

Unfortunately, with spare resources, this consequently drew the attention away from the forum, which can be seen in Figure 15 as a drop in new content creation from November 2021. Currently (May 2022), the forum has 89 registered members, only 5 new members since the evaluation was conducted in M29 2021.

Figure 17: Community 'stickiness' (Sept. 2019 - May 2022)

Despite less efforts from the Reflow consortium to uphold the forum, community 'stickiness' continued to rise. Between March and May 2022, stickiness was as high as 65 percent. Which shows that the current registered members have been satisfied with the content on the platform.

In summary, even though measures on community stickiness have been good, the forum has gained few new members each quarter and the number of new sign-ups each quarter has been steadily decreasing after a peak in from June to August 2020. The interaction on the forum has been close to non-existing - which has resulted in the forum performing more as an archive. It has not become an innovative community of practice, but arguably a best practice/knowledge stewarding community.

Moreover, those that have continuously returned to the forum, although not contributing, plausibly have an interest and dedication to the topic. The forum has mainly served as a one-way communication channel, but a CoP does not necessarily require a high frequency of interaction and interaction between all members. A CoP can also be classified on its ability to make people feel part of a group, even if they do not actively interact. For instance, the centralised CoP of the forum, allows members who identify with the cause to feel part of a somewhat undefined group, without knowing all other members. Being part of such a community can thus contribute to the personal identification of a cause and potentially lead the "members" to be a sort of advocates. The CoP can quantitatively be measured and tracked, but there are also limits to what the data can demonstrate - for example new connections (personal messaging), use of the information, and inspiration to other projects.

3.3.5 Reflections

Through the Forum and the LinkedIn Group, the Reflow Project created spaces for practitioners within the field of circular and regenerative cities to learn from the Project, learn about the topic more generally, and interact with each other. This way, Reflow attempted to reach further than those immediately affected and involved in the pilot level solutions. In retrospect however, establishing a forum proved to be devious. As the evaluation shows, there is a big difference between practically creating the space and getting members who are actively engaging with each other and contributing to the knowledge sharing. Based on the experience during the Reflow Project, the following reflections are made on why the centralised CoP did not turn out as anticipated.

1. **The competition:** There has been a significant increase in digital platforms, webpages, LinkedIn Groups and organisations within the topic of circular economy, with which the Reflow CoP has competed for the audience's attention and dedication. For instance, there are 643 groups on LinkedIn with the term "circular economy" in the name at the time of writing (see Figure 18). Although there are to our knowledge, only one other online forum like the Reflow Forum, namely Nordic Circular Arena which launched in June 2021⁵, there are many other platforms which overlap in their aim and set-up. For instance, the European Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform connects practitioners across Europe, and further lists 164 other European CE online platforms⁶. In sum, there is no shortage of online spaces where everyone interested in the circular economy can come to learn and engage with others. Looking at the initial survey (see 3.3.1), where lack of time and the importance of integration with other platforms came out as limitations for participation, one could argue that the high competition for one might have reduced the member's available time to participate, which was aggravated by the lack of integration of the forum with other platforms. Following this, the forum did not obtain a critical mass of active members, which then becomes self-fulfilling, meaning that it further reduced the incentive for members to become active.

Figure 18: CE groups on LinkedIn

2. **The necessary resources:** In addition to the need for heavy marketing, the establishment of a forum, and getting it from a dormant to an active space requires investment from the organisers, to keep it alive. Until a culture has been established and the members feel ownership and are driving the community, the core needs to create the activity as most visitors will not feel comfortable to post or comment if the site seems empty⁷.

⁵ Nordic Circular hotspot (2022). About Nordic Circular Hotspot. Retrieved from: <https://nordiccircularhotspot.org/aboutus>

⁶ European Union (2019). European Circular Economy Networks/Platforms. Retrieved from: <https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/en/dialogue/existing-eu-platforms>

⁷ Chordhury A. (2022). How to Launch a Successful Online Community: A-step-by-Step Guide. Hubspot. Retrieved from <https://blog.hubspot.com/marketing/online-community-launch>

Connected to the above points, it can be argued that establishing an online Forum in a time-bound EU project comes with several challenges and limitations. As the competition is fierce, establishing a successful community requires significant investment in marketing, and time and human resources in igniting it and keeping it alive and active. For a project like Reflow, which essentially focuses on developing context-based innovative circular practices in a tight timeframe, there is limited resources for adequate marketing and active global engagement on a centralised-based CoP.

That said, there are measures that could have been done to counter these challenges, such as:

- More marketing and awareness raising among target audiences
 - For example, through paid advertisement to beat the algorithm and to position the product above organic growth.
- More resources allocated to post-launch of the forum
- More engaging questions to inspire discussions
- Integration with LinkedIn, so that articles could be shared from the forum to LinkedIn
- Actively connect physical activities / events with the forum

3.4 Other contributions to CoP from the centralised perspective

Apart from the Forum and the LinkedIn Group, Reflow has also contributed to external platforms with knowledge, and thereby taken part in other CoPs. For instance, CBS has written 13 case studies about both project level resources and pilot city solutions for the Knowledge hub (See Figure 3). Knowledge Hub is the open-collaborative library for case studies about the circular economy, created and curated by Circle Economy⁸. The platform functions as a Wikipedia for information about circular economy, where users (individuals or organisations) can both publish their own cases and edit other's. There are also topic collections, where contributions within the same topics are gathered. The cases from Reflow were added to the "cities collection", where other significant organisations in the field are also present, such as Circle Economy, ICLEJ and the Ellen MacArthur Foundation⁹.

⁸ Knowledge Hub (n.d). Discover and contribute practical examples of the circular economy. Circle Lab. Retrieved from: <https://knowledge-hub.circle-lab.com/>

⁹ Knowledge Hub (n.d). Search. Circle Lab. Retrieved from: https://knowledge-hub.circle-lab.com/search?search=reflow&_start=0

Last Updated April 21, 2022

The REFLOW Operating System

The Reflow Operating System (OS) is an open-source operating system, which with its combination of components...

Article / Report Copenhagen

Last Updated April 21, 2022

The Amsterdam Reflow Booklet

The municipality of Amsterdam, co-created the Amsterdam RELOW Booklet, which describes circular solutions for the textil...

Article / Report Amsterdam

Last Updated April 21, 2022

Paris – RE-Label, a local certification of circularity

One of the outcomes of Paris' participation in the REFLOW project, is the development of a new certification, RE-Label, of...

Business case Paris

Last Updated April 21, 2022

Milan – digitalisation as an enabler of circular food markets in an urban context

During its participation at the REFLOW project, Milan focused on specific food flows to test new food prototypes, support existin...

Business case Milan

Figure 19: Screenshot from Reflow Cases on the Knowledge Hub

Further, Reflow has contributed with cases to the Covenant of Mayors, which can be read about in D7.4 - Collaboration with Covenant of Mayors and External Communities report.

4 De-centralised Reflow Communities of practice

4.1 Introduction

The different pilot cities have all engaged actively with the local community, both in terms of the overarching topic of circularity in cities, and topics more specific to their respective material flow. These local and more specialised CoPs have been open to a broad range of stakeholders, gathering people from many different fields based on a common wish to understand and work for more circular cities.

The de-centralised communities, in their capacity of face-to-face interactions, have been more able to facilitate incidental and unintended learning from each other and together, and have therefore taken the form of both *Helping Communities*, opening for small-scale and practical exchanges, and *Innovation Communities*, where new knowledge, ideas and practices are created. In addition, some of the work of the pilots can be qualified as *Stewarding Communities* where knowledge and best practices have been shared with the community.

At the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic, it was expected that the de-centralised CoPs would be infeasible as most countries restricted physical interactions. However, the local CoPs found new ways of interacting, which points to the value of local networks and co-creation and their sometimes-greater flexibility compared to larger and more structured CoPs. Further, the de-centralised CoPs have interacted across locations with other CoPs in the project, cross-pollinating between practitioners and topics.

The following section presents how each pilot has worked with CoP locally, and thereafter, how pilots have collaborated with other pilots and WPs. As the impact of the de-centralised CoP is hardly measurable, the section does not present concrete outcomes of the work, but qualitatively shows how the pilot cities of Reflow have been acting as catalysts for local engagement.

The reader should have in mind that as the pilots have operated within different topics and scenarios, and have had different focus areas, they have created different types of communities and for different types of stakeholders. For instance, Vejle has had a strong citizen focus, and have therefore created workshops and events with the aim of attracting and engaging citizens. Berlin on the other side, has had more a focus on industry, and their activities have therefore been more targeted such stakeholders.

The section of the pilot CoPs is divided according to the *activities* organised, such as *workshops, events, meetings, and conferences*. This because different activities engage the stakeholders differently, and therefore represent different types of communities. For instance, a presentation at a conference provides information and can be classified more as Best Practice Communities, whereas facilitating a workshop where the participants get to explore in practice and discuss the topic is more in line with an innovation Community. However, as the line between the different types of communities is often blurry, and one event can have components of several types, the section is divided into types of activities.

4.2 Pilot per pilot (sub communities)

4.2.1 Amsterdam

During Reflow, focusing on citizen engagement and local stakeholders, Amsterdam aligned various policy makers in the municipal area, local makers, and citizens to develop a circular vision as well as contributing to textile specific solutions. Contributing to the citizens scenario, Amsterdam carried out a citizen awareness campaign, which included an educational program, various workshops, and events (online and offline), circular kits and guidelines, four online workshops, 15 live-cast events and a festival about circular textiles.

Educational program: The educational program, in form of workshops, was designed to teach the participants how to reuse, repair, reduce, rethink, and recycle their wardrobe. The workshops provided educational opportunities for citizens to learn how to repair holes in their clothes by revisiting the ancient craft of visible mending techniques, and thereby extending the life cycle of their existing wardrobe. A handbook including a step-by-step approach of each technique was designed and recordings of the workshops can be found and downloaded online for further dissemination. Further, Amsterdam aimed to engage citizens across age through further educational offers. This has included reaching children in 15 primary schools as part of the Textile Race in the city. As part of this fun and engaging programme for children, the Amsterdam pilot involved 45 classes of around 25 students who were all tackling the challenge of textile waste in the city of Amsterdam. In total the educational program reached 1000 citizens (further information in D1.5). The pilot also engaged children through workshops at OBA (The Amsterdam Public Library Foundation) on "The world of clothing". The pilot also carried out workshops with students at KABK (Royal Academy of Arts) and at the Gerrit Rietveld Academie on "Don't let your textiles go to waste" where they engaged with citizens who were given the tools and knowledge on how to reuse, repair, reduce, rethink, recycle, and revalue their wardrobes. More details about this work can be found in D1.3.

Awareness campaign: In Amsterdam's awareness campaign for citizens, composed of online and offline workshops, citizen guides, circular kits (e.g., Monday laundry days), the city engaged citizens and makers across sectors. In collaboration with art schools, the municipality collaborated on circular textile practices and designs. A following exhibition of their work presented the results of the workshops. To further increase citizen awareness and action, the Amsterdam pilot hosted a series of four online Reflow workshops. The workshops and the series of 15 live casts collaborated with local universities and other local actors. The topics of the workshops and live casts were closely connected with the focus and solution of the pilot and ranged from the growing number of wasted textiles to bio-based materials and tools for the conscious consumer and business models like sharing, renting and repairing.

As a further step of citizen engagement, the Reflow Circular Textile Festival in Pakhuis de Zwijgerin was a space for professionals and those interested in circular textiles and clothing coming together to show how things can be done differently. The festival was a space for workshops, talks, film screening, clothing exchange and networking opportunities, and was planned to be a kick-off for further circular actions in Amsterdam. Through the listed activities, all contributing to a bottom-up approach, the Amsterdam pilot contributed significantly to the local discussion and conversation about circularity in the textile and fashion industry.

Trough concrete solutions such as the Denim Deal and the Amsterdam Reflow Booklet, Amsterdam does not only educate about circular textile use, but also provides an alliance across the value chain of denim. The Denim Deal gives certainty to all involved actors over the production process and new industry standards of denim and textile products. Aligning all actors in the value chain, Amsterdam contributed to a more collaborative ecosystem in the denim industry.

Figure 20: Photo of the Reflow Amsterdam team attending the Circular Textile Days in Pakhuis de Zwijger

4.2.2 Berlin

During Reflow, Berlin aligned various policy makers in the municipal area, local and national organisations, and citizens to develop a circular vision for wastewater heat recovery. Contributing to its scenarios of developing, implementing and replicating technologies enabling the shift towards circularity, Berlin engaged in various events and Interactions with citizens to contribute to the local discussion around wastewater heat recovery.

Events: Berlin’s aim is to increase awareness and foster fruitful discussions about wastewater heat recovery in Germany. Through various events, the pilot contributed to the local discussion of circular wastewater use. The pilot took part in at the Berliner Energietage, DWA Energietage, Sitzung der Plattform, Kommunale Wärmewende – Zukunft der Infrastrukturen and Arbeitskreis Quartier. During the events, the pilot presented the wastewater heat potential map to stakeholders of the heat energy community. The pilot received feedback from local stakeholders of the community and contributed to the general discussion and awareness of the topic, strengthening the community around this topic in particular.

Figure 21. Picture of discussion with infrastructure firms in Berlin

Video and workshops: The Berlin pilot created a video about wastewater heat recovery and distributed it among citizen and stakeholders. Further workshops with a mix of stakeholders such as interested citizens and experts, engaged local actors in the process of wastewater heat recovery. In collaboration with CityLab, the pilot facilitated workshops, social media events and newsletters, which enabled early user testing.

4.2.3 Cluj-Napoca

During Reflow, focusing on citizen engagement and local stakeholders, Cluj-Napoca aligned various policy makers in the municipal area, local makers, and citizens to develop a vision on energy efficiency. Contributing to its scenarios, Cluj-Napoca carried out educational workshops, participated at an international conference and contributed to the implementation of circular policies.

Awareness raising campaign: As part of its awareness raising approach, the pilot offered educational workshops. In collaboration the university of UBB- School of Economics University Leadership, a master course was composed to increase awareness in academia as well in the next curricula. The workshops engage key civic actors sharing their profound knowledge on energy efficiency and circular actions. Further workshops focused on schools and young citizens. The workshops aimed to increase the connection between the understanding of circular economy and energy efficiency and the regarding actions, which can be taken to become more energy efficient. Further focus was to highlight and educate about the socio-economic benefits of energy efficiency.

Conferences: The pilot participated at the Transylvanian Cluster International conference 2021 (TCIC). The conference is an annual event organized by the Northern Transylvania Clusters Consortium, aiming to support the economic environment and to facilitate the international exchange of knowledge and good practices, providing a cross-continental collaboration platform for addressing global challenges. Through its research in energy efficiency as a whole system approach the pilot contributed to the discussion of circular economy.

Meetings on policy infrastructure: In relation to its third scenario, the pilot has brought the topic of circular economy and the perspective of energy efficiency to several policy- and business-related environments. During meetings with the Digital Innovation Hub, the pilot development policy strategies such as the, the Regional Smart Specialization Strategy.

Figure 22: Photo of the Cluj Pilot facilitating a stakeholder meeting

4.2.4 Milan

Milan's commitment to sustainable food systems is already witnessed in its Urban Food Policy, one of the first dedicated policies across Europe. Within Reflow, the Milan pilot intervenes over a specific field of the food policy, namely the support to micro-enterprises and 'small' actors, yet in close collaboration with large enterprises such as So.Ge.Mi and Amsa. Furthermore, Manifattura Milano is the other key initiative of reference for the Reflow pilot, where the local network of Fab Labs and makerspaces is strategically involved to support the collaboration between the different actors within the local system of municipal covered markets.

Workshop participation and organisation: The Milan actively contributed to the local discussion of Circular Economy and circular food flows in an urban context. The team participated in the virtual workshop of the City Science Initiative. The workshop on Circular Economy was organised by European Commission and offered a space where representatives of cities (policy and research sides) and key stakeholders could interact. The focus was on working on circular economy at an urban level from the angle of European institutions, networks of cities, international projects such as CLIC and FORCE, national governments, and regions.

The Milan pilot also participated at the Open Talk: *As Good as Gold – From Waste to biomaterials*, which was organized by the city of Milan, OpenDot and Materiom involving the European project CENTRINNO, the organisations NEMA - Rete Nuove Manifatture (Cariplo Factory, alcube, BASE Milano, OpenDot, WeMake) and Politecnico di Milano University.

The Open Talk was followed by the 1,5-day workshop: *EAT.SAVE. MAKE | Learn how food waste can become biomaterial*. Materiom provided open-source recipes and data on materials made from local and abundant sources of natural ingredients, like unavoidable food waste. The session taught how to fabricate a range of biomaterials through distributed and sustainable practices and how to transform these materials thanks to digital fabrication tools.

Figure 23: Photo of the Milan pilot presenting at the Open Talk: *As Good as Gold – From Waste to biomaterials*

4.2.5 Paris

During Reflow, focusing on citizen engagement and local stakeholders, Paris aligned various policy makers in the municipal area, local makers, and citizens to develop a vision on circular timber use.

Showcases: Paris facilitated 31 showcases over the project with 2400 local makers and businesses participating, which included Fab Labs and makerspaces, circular economy stakeholders, industry stakeholders, investors, the

scientific and academic community, civil society, and policy makers. The showcases consisted of but were not limited to Pecha Kucha Night Paris, workshops hosted by Driven, incubation program call for projects, installations, trainings, website publications, and webinars. Through reaching out to local makers and businesses, the Paris pilot was able to spread the message and work of Reflow in their city and community, to activate the local ecosystem around reuse in the temporary construction and event industry, to engage with these stakeholders on the solutions they were developing, and to on board potential incubation projects in Driven. Data was tracked at these events by the Paris pilot including the name of showcase, description, level of involvement, date, number of attendees, type of attendees, and further links of information.

Live Sessions: The pilot designed live sessions with local actors in circular economy. The live sessions were carried out with partners such as Klaas of Bollinger + Grohmann architecture studio and highlighted circular topics about technology, architecture, and circular economy.

Events: In collaboration with Volumes, the pilot carried out three events in the Pecha Kucha format, focusing on the event industry and circular economy, with a refined emphasis on wood reuse at those events. The events allowed actors to come together around the topic, to be aware of the different initiatives in place, and to promote and give visibility to key stakeholders. The three events focused on creative hubs, communities, and projects in relation to local innovation and circularity. Further, the pilot offered a series of workshops focusing on technical innovations in the wood industry, published within the Driven program and featuring experts in the respective topic.

Figure 24: Pecha Kucha Night at Volumes Lab. Source: Volumes

Under the premises of all three scenarios, the pilot was reaching and activating workshops through three training sessions (Circular Making, online workshop in Nancy, and Résiliences Productives) hosted and created by the Paris pilot. These trainings have reached and activated 47 makers and workshops in the pilot's target group including those remote from employment, designers, architects, artisans, creators, and engineers. The Résiliences Productives training resulted in the workshops and makers involved creating a community on Re-Label.

4.2.6 Vejle

Through webinars, workshops, an exhibition, and a conference, the Vejle pilot has interacted and engaged with local residents, local makers, entrepreneurs, and businesses.

Workshops: In Spinderihallerne the Vejle pilot hosted a workshop on biomaterials together with Materiom and CBS. Here, creative and designers, university students, schoolteachers and a design researcher working in the Food Lab H2020 project, were invited to a hand-on workshop about the making of bio plastics, led by Materiom. At this workshop, there were about 10-12 participants from varied backgrounds: creative and designers, university students, schoolteachers and a design researcher working in the Food Lab H2020 project. CBS was also present, discussing the business opportunities with bio plastic with the participants. For the Fablab Spinderihallerne, this was an opportunity to mature their biomaterials knowledge for the future creation of a Bio Lab in the facility. Given this, the fab lab team and Materiom's team briefly discussed a potential future collaboration to develop the Bio Lab. As a consequence of the headquarters of the Vejle pilot being based at Spinderihallerne, 10 local makers in the FabLab were also involved in the creation of a BioLab, a part of the FabLab.

The Vejle pilot also organised and facilitated workshops held at their test sites (Den Gamle Gård, Sofiegården, and REMA 1000). At these test site workshops, the Vejle pilot engaged 12 businesses including REMA 1000, Cloetta, Marius Pedersen ApS, and P. Fournaise. Reaching these businesses through the test site showcases proved to be crucial in the Vejle pilot's co-creation processes, gaining feedback, and understanding of the reality of needs of the actors on the ground.

Educational programs: With a large focus on engaging and empowering the citizens of Vejle, the pilot city has engaged 277 citizens through educational programmes over the course of the Reflow project. Educational programmes included a biomaterial workshop and plastic workshop where citizens could interact with plastic waste and rethink its value and use as a resource. Importantly, the Vejle pilot has worked with several exhibitions, to ensure a broader involvement of citizens, that makes the complex project more perceptible, visual, and tangible.

Exhibition and conference: An exhibition at Spinderihallerne engaged students with teaching materials and with the installations at the exhibition on plastic and Reflow. Students were from the Southern University of Denmark, Brandbjerg Højskole, and the 10th grade Youth Center Vejle. The exhibitions are co-created by a wide range of stakeholders – Artist Maria Viftrup, the Innovation Team in Spinderihallerne Vejle Municipality, The Southern Danish business college (SDE), FabLab, designers, Waste Management Vejle, entrepreneurs and SMEs, Aage Vestergaard Larsen, Danish Design Center and many more.

Figure 25. Images from the workshop on bio plastic in Vejle

In addition to the expedition, Vejle has hosted a conference: The Future is Now: Radical experiments with circular economy. The conference was aimed to inspire, provide tools and learning on circular economy from a more practical and explorative perspective for the local community, hosting researchers, local politicians, and circular economy experts.

Lastly, at Den Gamle Gård test site, the pilot city engaged with the residents at the apartment block in the West of Vejle at an event, attracting 70 citizens. In collaboration with AAB Housing association and the plastic recycler Aage Vestergaard Larsen a flowerpot prototype for the garden in Den Gamle Gård was made by Wild Studio using recycled household plastic. The flowerpots were made to create awareness on recycling of plastic at Den Gamle Gård.

4.3 Across pilots (cross pollination) and WP + pilot interactions + WP communities

Cross pollination of knowledge between REFLOW members

Beyond the active interventions related to engaging an active community of circular economy practitioners at global and local level, it is worth mentioning that in this in-between space, several practices emerged between REFLOW partners, which led to increased knowledge transfer. These practices were not planned per se within tasks and work packages activities but became visible as new needs from the community appeared.

Online digital literacy development

With the unexpected pandemic events, members of REFLOW quickly realised that physical co-creation activities could not be performed as initially planned. The need to come up with new digital solutions to perform the work led the community to self-organise, share good practices on relevant digital tools, develop peer learning sessions on the most useful tools, which eventually led to the generalisation of a shared online process to conduct online workshops (through Miro).

Reflow OS community of practice

Beyond the specific tasks and activities focusing on the development of the REFLOW OS (WP2) and its implementation (WP5), one saw the emergence of active discussions and knowledge exchange around the tools developed on dedicated github pages. Discussions between WP2 partners, Tech representatives at pilot levels and the global OS community at large emerged as the tech solutions came to shape.

Organic knowledge exchange between partners

Through the numerous hours of online meetings dedicated to specific tasks and activities, partners also indirectly became aware of other partners' competences and skills, which eventually led to organic knowledge transfer. One illustration can be crystallised in the collaborative development of the Driven incubator coaching process between Paris-based Volumes and Finland-based Ecovala, the latter sharing knowledge and tools on circular business model innovation to support incubated start-ups.

5 Conclusion

This deliverable shows how the Reflow project has both been the source of and contributed actively to, a range of communities of practice across different formats and topics.

On a project level, significant resources were invested in creating and maintaining both the forum and the LinkedIn group, including evaluation and iterations. The forum managed to collect and share many resources about CE in cities and enjoyed a relatively large community. In a centralised manner, Reflow thereby created a community of practice around the project and the topic in general. Nonetheless, there were challenges connected with the feasibility of building up an online forum within a time-limited project, and in retrospect the format was potentially not the most suited for an EU project. This constitutes an important lesson for future projects.

On a pilot level, the cities have been active both in initiating, developing, and maintaining de-centralised communities throughout the project, despite challenges associated with Covid-19. The de-centralised communities differed between and within pilots in terms of type of activity and thereby their type of community, from best practice - and knowledge communities, to the more active innovation communities. This way, they could reach a broad range of stakeholders and cover many topics. This proved beneficial as we are dealing with a transition towards a new reality, and communities therefore needed a mix between getting knowledge, a space to discuss, and a space to innovate. Although they were time-bound, they contributed to the general local community, and the feeling of togetherness around the different topics.

In sum, the Reflow project has managed to spread knowledge and best practices about circularity in cities in general, as well as more specialised topics related to the theme, and engaged all target audiences in knowledge sharing and innovation.

Hopefully, the seeds planted within the communities of practice created during the Reflow project will continue to have an impact on the participants, for instance by having inspired them to continue to be interested in and work for a transition to circular cities.

Learnings and recommendation:

- 1. Finding the space:** Especially for centralised and online communities, it is necessary to find the right "space" for the community to emerge, expand and thrive. Online communities require significant resources to engage the community, especially if the aim is active communication and knowledge sharing between the members. Local decentralised COP may be more efficient as it is easier to align objectives and needs between local members.
- 2. Connecting with existing platforms and communities:** Following the above point, it might therefore not be optimal to start from scratch and creating a new platform for a time-limited project. Rather, an easier and more effective way could be to join forces with other communities and platforms, for instance in the form of a sub-group on an existing forum.
- 3. Finding the balance:** The activation of both a centralised and de-centralised communities was beneficial to reach a large audience across topics. It is however a need to find a balance between centralised/decentralised, online/offline, and most importantly, to connect both in order to leverage the abilities of each.
- 4. Adaptive community management:** Community management is both crucial and challenging. "Pushing" strategies are not necessarily efficient, and rather one should start from the individual needs (finding information, communicating challenges, cocreate) and adapt the response of the structure based on

these needs. Learning to iterate and "sense" how the community can work together is crucial to reach its full potential.

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Appendix 1

Skills needs assessment report

Wp6 - Ecovala

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

Objective of the survey

Skills needs

In order to tailor the training resources to the needs of active stakeholders at city level, it is necessary to identify and assess the skills and competences needed for each stakeholder and second, prioritize the skills that should be developed further based on existing levels of competence.

Finally, it is also important to grasp how individuals generally want to learn.

PROFILE OF RESPONDENTS

Functions
Experience
Motivations

BERLIN

Revamping public property

AMSTERDAM

Textile life cycling

MILAN

Food Markets 2.0

VEJLE

Circular plastics

CLUJ-NAPOCA

pienergy

PARIS

Fairtracker

1. What is your main function in relation to the transition of your city towards circular economy?

2. How long have you been working on the topic?

3. What motivates you to develop new competences with regards to your current role?

*Personal interest explore possibilities that we haven't even yet imagined / drive technology to crucial human challenges

VISIONS OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY

A portfolio of visions within the community

Holistic visions

“Circular economy as a way to develop solutions to recirculate resource flows, while engaging citizens and other stakeholders to co-create meaningful solutions”

“Circular economy as an economy system in which we move from a linear process of extraction - transformation - consumption - waste, into a circular one in which a higher utility and value is extracted from resources. This involves higher recovering, regenerating, reusing and recycling of materials and products, through generating new goods, new uses and engaging new users. This transition would involve cities to shift from consuming and wasting into producing and transforming.”

“Circular economy as a re-ideation of our local economy and city, that implies change from everything, and everybody involved or connected in this city.”

“Circular economy as a vision achievable when all the actors involved find their place and the environment in which they aim to do so, is enabling.”

“Circular Economy as a set of complementary elements that form a concept.

It is a vision of a sustainable and viable ecosystem (from socio-economical-environmental perspectives), that is self sustainable, adapts constantly and always involves society as a whole.”

Resource- centered visions

"Creating a city where as little waste as possible is generated, and where waste is regarded as a resource".

"An economic and ecological system aimed at eliminating waste"

"increasing the circularity of material flows"

"Material reused , upcycled, recycled"

Governance- centered visions

"CE is a process that needs both top-down and bottom-up approach".

"Circular economy is a new way of being a food consumer, promoter, producers and seller."

"The latter requires a new mind-set for citizenship, that actually represents the core of the transition. I think that the main effort of the project must focus on citizen engagement and on the implementation phase".

Technology- centered visions

“We are challenging Circular Economy with Digital Tools and Knowledge in order to maximize impact of our projects”

Business- centered visions

"An opportunity for business creation, new jobs"

"Companies play a bigger part by self-help and being resilient to preventing the challenges of tomorrow"

"it is our belief, that new business-models will show the way forward"

Behaviour- centered visions

"Circular economy is based on a deep transformation of habits and behaviour, but with a clear environmental goal."

"Circular Economy is purposive, but isn't just about sustainability environmentally, the socio-economic components are fundamental for this transition to happen."

"This happens in mindset and cultural rituals: from the way we consume, purchase and dispose, all the way to how we see and value resources present or even abundant around us."

"Circular economy is important in order to increase citizens's quality of life"

Challenge- centered visions

“reduction of the amounts of discarded and destroyed/incinerated textiles”

“We have to use textile products much longer and have to recycle discarded textiles into secondary fibers which can be used again in high added value textile products”

“Reusing waste water for private households or businesses.”

“Introduce circularity in event and support the actors of the circular Economy.”

“Circular Economy in energy is related in what is the flow of the energy in the city. Energy which enter in the city through providers and how this energy is consumed and what remain (pollution, losses, etc...)”

**CHALLENGES
FACED IN
DAILY
ACTIVITIES**

Complexity
digital culture
Infrastructure needs
Common understanding
Competitiveness
Scaling up
Cultural mindset
Implementation
Citizen engagement
Business involvement
Data alliance
Monitoring
Business support
Stakeholders
Material knowledge
Behaviour change
Concrete actions

FROM THEORY TO IMPLEMENTATION

- Poor capacity to make actionable strategies that can translate into concrete roadmaps;
- Difficulty to find a practical implementation of CE strategy
- Complexity in operationalization of solutions
- Challenge in translating the topic into practice

CULTURAL CHALLENGE

- shifting mindset
- Behavioral issues

CITIZENS ENGAGEMENT

- Concrete actions that can be taken by everyone to promote Circular Economy. many people like the idea of circular economy but don't know where to start in their everyday choices, both in their job as well as in their private life.
- Lack of awareness of citizens
- make the topic tangible and comprehensible for all target groups

BUSINESS CHALLENGE

- The challenge is to help local actors to be competitive.
- Getting businesses involved
- Scaling up issues for businesses
- Lack of Business Advisor Skills

GOVERNANCE CHALLENGES

- Alignment with different stakeholders

TECHNOLOGICAL CHALLENGES

- Poor Digital Culture of the designers and makers
- The lack of data alliance between private and public parties
- Lack of material science expertise

THEORETICAL CHALLENGES

- Lack of common understanding
- Complexity

COMPETENCES

Assesment of importance of competences in 5 skills sets

Systems thinking competences
Values thinking competences
Future thinking competences
Technical competences
Interpersonal competences

4. Based on your role and responsibilities, please appreciate the importance of the following knowledge whereby "

FOCUS NEEDED ON:

KNOWLEDGE: knowledge of different roles of actors and understanding the interplay between different actors.

SKILLS: map important stakeholders and initiate dialogue with them

COMPETENCE: manage interdisciplinary cooperation in relation to economic, social and environmental assessment at city level

Suggestion: Stakeholder management as part of upcoming toolkit

5. Based on your role and responsibilities, please appreciate the importance of the following competences whereby

FOCUS NEEDED ON:

KNOWLEDGE: understanding of how sustainability and circularity concepts vary across and within cultures

SKILLS: use methods such as visioning, multi-criteria impact assessment, and risk assessment

COMPETENCE : Have the ability to collaborate with stakeholders to specify, negotiate, and apply sustainability values, principles, objectives, and goals.

Suggestion: Stakeholder management as part of upcoming toolkit

6. Based on your role and responsibilities, please appreciate the importance of the following competences whereby "No answer"=Neutral

FOCUS NEEDED ON:

KNOWLEDGE:

- Have understanding of the concepts of sustainability and circular economy in a local and global context
- Knowledge of different models for the development and design of cities with a sustainability and circularity approach and the impacts of these models

Recommendation: Circular economy 101 learning resources. Focus on general concept, and different entry point: governance, tech, business models, etc..

7. Based on your role and responsibilities, please appreciate the importance of the following competences whereby “No answer”=Neutral

FOCUS NEEDED ON:

KNOWLEDGE: on new technological approaches to the promotion of sustainable innovation

SKILLS:

- assess and combine different approaches to promoting sustainability and circular economy in an urban context
- combine and use relevant theories, understandings, methods and analyses in such a way that these form a synthesis aimed at the formulation of concrete strategies and plans for the work of the city with sustainable solutions

COMPETENCES:

- Assess economic, social and environmental impacts in relation to sustainable urban development

Recommendation:

- Development of learning resources on the role of new tech
- Multi level perspective resources.
- Actionable toolkit based on a variety of methods and tools
- Learning resources on social impact assessment

8. Based on your role and responsibilities, please appreciate the importance of the following competences

FOCUS NEEDED ON:

KNOWLEDGE: understand the potentials and challenges in the development of cooperation relations, including public-private partnerships, networks, etc.

SKILLS: communicate the result of projects to a selected target audience

COMPETENCES: initiate and participate in interdisciplinary planning tasks and cooperation across social levels, nationalities and cultures

Recommendation:

- “Communicating circularity” learning resources.
- Citizen engagement resources.
- Planning/action plan development/ cooperation resources.

9. Can you prioritise the set of competences for which you would need to receive training/additional resources?

10. Through which medium do you prefer acquiring new knowledge? (several answers possible)

*Distributed workshops (online/offline) / online consultancy

11. Duration of training you normally take?

12. Which technology do you normally use in your learning?

RECOMMENDATION

- Development of generic online resources. Access to existing resources.
- Focus on short content

- Cocreation of specific resources to be used in workshop format
 - slide deck of content to be used in workshop / seminars
 - specific toolkits designed to be self-usable in local context

13. Which learning resources would you prefer accessing in relation to your work related to circular cities?

Number of respondents: 20, selected answers: 161

RECOMMENDATION

Focus on:

- Short inspirational content (3.35)
- Practical Toolkits (3.2)
- How to guidance (average: (3.05)
- Webinars (3.1)
- Business case databases (2.95)
- Circular policy databases (2.62)
- Ecourse (2,45)

14. Any additional skills/competences that you would like to acquire in relation to circular cities transition?

- Business model development
- Material science
- Carbon footprint analysis
- Raising funding for initiatives
- Codesign
- data

Additional learning resources/material needed?

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 [REFLOWproject](https://www.facebook.com/REFLOWproject)

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 info@reflowproject.eu

Appendix 2

Reflow CoP

Basic report

REFLOW COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

Total number of respondents: 9

1. As someone interested and working in the field of circular economy, would you join an online community where you can connect and interact with other individuals interested in circular economy?

Number of respondents: 9

	n	Percent
YES	8	88.89%
NO	1	11.11%

2. What may be the reason to (not) do so?

Number of respondents: 6

Responses
Access new knowledge
Receive up to date content and tools
To exchange knowledge, connect with other projects, find solutions on how to tackle common challenges.
As Wp2 leads we would like to know people opinions about our work so far and the use of tech tools
I am already part of a network of individuals connected/interested to CE, both offline and online through different platforms.
Not do: If it becomes overload and unstructured Do: If it is inspirational and provides opportunities.

3. What specific CE-related topics do you find interesting? (multiple choices possible)

Number of respondents: 9 , selected answers: 36

	n	Percent
Circular cities strategies	5	55.56%
Citizen practices /citizen engagement	8	88.89%
Circular Business models	6	66.67%
Circular policies	6	66.67%
Circular technologies	5	55.56%
Education for a circular economy	6	66.67%
Other	0	0%

Answers given into free text field

Option names	Text

4. How important do you consider the following features of an online community?

Number of respondents: 9

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Important	Fairly important	Very important	Average	Median
Have facilitators / community managers	0%	12.5%	37.5%	12.5%	37.5%	3.75	3.5
Critical mass of active members	0%	12.5%	12.5%	50%	25%	3.88	4
Great User Experience	0%	0%	33.33%	22.22%	44.45%	4.11	4
Possibility to upload/share knowledge	0%	0%	22.22%	22.22%	55.56%	4.33	5
Regular interaction	0%	25%	37.5%	37.5%	0%	3.13	3
Gamification aspects (badges)	50%	25%	12.5%	12.5%	0%	1.88	1.5
Private messaging	25%	25%	37.5%	0%	12.5%	2.5	2.5
Searchable repository	0%	11.11%	22.22%	11.11%	55.56%	4.11	5
Other (specify)	0%	0%	0%	33.33%	66.67%	4.67	5

Answers given into free text field

Option names	Text
Other (specify)	Integrates well with existing platforms, e.g. LinkedIn
Other (specify)	A place to receive feedback for other Reflow tech
Other (specify)	Participants should commit to a methodology of knowledge sharing

5. What are for you personally the most important reasons for participating in the REFLOW community?

Number of respondents: 9

	1	2	3
Hearing about new knowledge and experiences from other community members	75%	0%	25%
Developing new ideas together	25%	75%	0%
Developing standards, methods and best practices	100%	0%	0%
Making useful contacts/networking	0%	80%	20%
Improving the level of expertise of the members	0%	33.33%	66.67%
Staying up to date in the topic of the community	0%	50%	50%
Saving time in finding all kinds of information	20%	0%	80%
None	-	-	-
Other (specify):	100%	0%	0%

6. If applicable, what would strongly limit your ability to participate in the REFLOW CoP?

Number of respondents: 9 , selected answers: 15

	n	Percent
Lack of time	5	55.56%
Lack of incentives	3	33.33%
Already participating in other online communities	3	33.33%
Other (specify)	4	44.44%

7. Are you already involved in other virtual communities?

Number of respondents: 8

	n	Percent
Yes (which one)	4	50%
No	3	37.5%
Don't know	1	12.5%

Answers given into free text field

Option names	Text
Yes (which one)	Impact Hub Network
Yes (which one)	Fab City/Precious Plastic/many on linkedIn
Yes (which one)	LinkedIn, knowledge coming in through newsletters, blog posts, etc.
Yes (which one)	Open source dev community